

Good management of Trichoderma, the green mold disease

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The problem

Trichoderma, caused by the homonymous fungal pathogen, drives production losses during mushroom cultivation. It is transmitted by vectors (flies and mites), favored by high humidity and temperature, and associated with improper compost pasteurization.

The solution

Growers can treat Trichoderma with phytosanitary products, based on *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens*. Correct management of the crop and sanitation remain the only preventive measures.

Benefits

Preventive measures can reduce economic losses due lost production and costs of phytosanitary products.

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Practical recommendations

Identify disease outbreaks early: visit the crop regularly and visually check the casing material and the compost.

(1) Recommendations for when the disease has appeared:

- Minimize air currents.
- Avoid irrigation on Trichoderma (that would disperse spores).
- Avoid touching the affected surface. If you do, change your gloves immediately.
- As a harvester, disinfect your hands with hand sanitizer before and after putting on gloves.

(2) Recommendations to prevent appearance:

Maintenance:

- Disinfect your work tools before and after use.
- Work from the most recent to the oldest crop.
- Discard leftover casing material from previous crops.
- Store casing containers in a clean area.
- Use well pasteurized compost, without excess of ammonia.
- Control the humidity and temperature of the growing chambers.

Vectors:

- Use air filters, adhesive plates with pheromones, and black lights in the gates.

About BIOSCHAMP and this Practice Abstract

This practice abstract was elaborated in the BIOSCHAMP project, based on the EIP AGRI practice abstract format. © 2024

Project dates: from October 2020 to September 2024.

Goal: develop an integrated approach to tackle the mushroom cultivation challenges, improving the mushroom sector industrial profitability while reducing the agronomical need for pesticides by 90 %.